

While Moving Hiring A Day Labour Is Good Option Or Not?

You are all prepared for DIY move done your packing, rented a moving truck, but the ones who are going to assist you said No at the last moment and now you are stuck with ohh god what should I do, just take a deep breath and relax, I know handling all this loading and unloading is not one person job, we definitely need some assistance to make the move on the date you decided. You don't wanna hire a full moving service, then go for one day labour, wanna know more about hiring any labour and where you can find out just follow this [Packers And Movers In Mumbai](#) guide.

What is day labour?

In full moving services you get the moving services from top to down means from packing to unpacking but in day labour hiring you need to take care of packing, renting a moving truck, unpacking at new home and for loading and unloading they can assist. Most labour charge according to the hours so before hiring one ask them about their hourly rate and the estimate time to load your belongings into the truck.

Can you count them as professionals?

Many moving company also give facility of sending their labour for day job, this type of worker is licence and have experienced since they work for the moving company. However if you decided to hire a day labour who is rookie and are not licensed then keep in mind you are taking the chance and won't be compensated in case of any damage and what about

the credibility. [Packers and Movers in Mumbai](#) give their customer an option to go for full #moving services or for assistance in #loading and #unloading or only in #packing

Who will bring the moving equipment's?

For day labour you need to bring moving vehicle for transportation and other required materials for moving, like moving dolly, moving blankets, truck ramps, tie downs and rope for fixing the furniture's in truck. Day labour if not from Movers side won't provide you with these equipment's you yourself should take the responsibility of these items because it's your belongings.

Some pros and cons attached to bring a day labour:

Pros

It's affordable:

It's affordable to hire day labour than going for full moving services, off course they do a lot a whole bunch of work, but when you can handle packing and renting vehicle then going only for day labour can spend well. Also full services Will Definitely are high then day labour, as day labour is only providing loading facility on hourly basis.

Full control:

Except unloading and loading you will be handling all other jobs you have a great flexibility in doing that whenever you want you can start for it whenever you like. Also when it comes to #transporting you will be doing it with yourself so there is no delay in receiving the goods.

Keeps you away from injury:

Lifting a heavy furniture and boxes is not a good idea because we are not aware of the techniques and holds no experience in it, even you think that lifting heavy item's can be easy but it's lot different to lift heavy

furniture in normal life and when you are moving. Now **#moving** **#bike** is easy than ever with the help of *Packers and Movers in Mumbai*.

Cons:

But it's expensive:

While day labour charges are less than full moving services but it's a lot more than doing a DIY move on your own and with the support of your friends and family. If you can then delay your moving date until your friends who promised you to help will come.

No liability coverage:

While full moving services professionals are registered and licence day labour's are not until you are hiring labour from moving company. Before you hire day labour it's important to ask them about the liability cause in case of damage who will be responsible and when. Also check your own moving insurance to see what is covered and what is not.

Where to find day labour:

Hire free lancers:

In every city you will find a free lancers, if you don't know where that spot then search for it is and hire a day labour from there but before you choose any ask what their hourly rate is. **#Local #Packers and #Movers in #Mumbai** price for moving depends on services you available and goods you are moving means no extra hidden cost.

Students:

If you know some students who can help you out in your move then gather your group, you may need to know when their schedule is free and will they happily willing to help you out. If it's a local move then they can help you out in both unloading and loading but if its long distance move it may not be possible for them to help you out unless they travel with you.

Movers:

Call movers for asking them do they provide day labour facility, if yes then ask them what their hourly rate is or how they charge.

Now you got your option evaluate and choose which one you will go for. **#Packers and #Movers #Mumbai** help in #moving #insurance too.

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